

TECHNOLOGIES FOR ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT EDUCATION OF STUDENTS IN A DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: In this article, in the digital educational environment, it is necessary to establish systematic work in the implementation of the independent education process in higher educational institutions, to teach students to work independently, to be creative and socially active, who have the skills to independently find their place in social and political life, to set promising tasks and to solve them. will be the basis for forming a new generation of personnel with the ability to do.

Key words: digital education system, independent education, credit module, independent thinking.

Chapter 3 of the Concept of the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, entitled "Strategic Goals and Priority Areas of the Development of the Higher Education System", § 1, entitled "Expanding the coverage of higher education, improving the quality of training of highly educated specialists", "Independent education hours" increasing the share of students, independent education, critical and creative thinking, systematic analysis, formation of entrepreneurship skills, introduction of methods and technologies aimed at strengthening competencies in the educational process, directing the educational process to the formation of practical skills, in this regard, advanced pedagogical technologies based on international educational standards for the educational process, wide introduction of educational programs and educational methodological materials, independent education of learners, necessary competence of specialists through continuous improvement of independent work skills Special attention is paid to the development of intelligence, creativity, research, and logical thinking.¹

The reforms carried out in the educational system today are aimed at the development of independent thinking of students, based on individual educational trajectories, and elimination of problems related to the formation of creative thinking and practical skills in students. A step-by-step transition to the implementation of these tasks is planned in higher education institutions.

Today, the main problems in the higher education system are the lack of independent study hours, students' lack of independent learning, critical and creative thinking, systematic analysis, entrepreneurship skills, organizational ability of students in the educational process, introduction of methods and technologies aimed at strengthening competencies. Therefore, in the higher education system, it is necessary to increase the share of independent study hours, students' independent education, critical and creative thinking, systematic analysis, formation of entrepreneurial skills, introduction of methods and technologies aimed at strengthening

¹ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 International PF-4947 Decree No. PF-4947 "People's Word", February 8, 2017

competencies in the educational process, orienting the educational process to the formation of practical skills, in this regard One of the main tasks of today is the widespread introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies, educational programs and educational materials based on international educational standards into the educational process.

In modern conditions, it is demanded that the educational process should be directed to the development, socialization and training of independent, critical and creative thinking abilities. It is necessary to train highly qualified specialists according to the requirements of consumers, to form the knowledge, skills and qualifications of students in their chosen specialties, to independently acquire knowledge and to train them in practical activities.

Due to the fact that independent education is interpreted as a problem for the development of students' organizational skills, the new version of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" approved on September 23, 2020 states that "Independent education is carried out individually and the professional, intellectual, spiritual and cultural development of students is serves" can be mentioned.²

In the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the further development of the higher education system": "Each higher education institution should establish close partnership relations with the world's leading scientific and educational institutions, use advanced pedagogical technologies, curricula and training programs based on international educational standards in the educational process. wide introduction of methodological materials, active involvement of highly qualified teachers and scientists from foreign partner educational institutions in educational and pedagogical activities, conducting master classes, training courses...

Currently, further improvement of the educational process, curricula and programs of higher education on the basis of the wide introduction of new pedagogical technologies and teaching methods, the qualitative renewal of the master's scientific-educational process and the introduction of modern organizational forms are among the main problems. The main goal is to create a new generation of widely introduced new pedagogical technologies and teaching methods, qualitatively update the master's scientific-educational process, and introduce modern organizational forms.

In the conditions of today's globalization, it is desirable to use advanced pedagogical technologies and active methods in the educational process, to apply newly produced technical tools, to encourage more students to work independently, and to widely use various ways of teaching lessons from best practices. Another important point is that it is necessary to ensure the effective organization of training of special subjects in order to develop the inclination, abilities, knowledge and skills of students studying in the higher education system, to develop them as specialists in their chosen fields.

As in any society, the main problem in the development of our republic is the training of qualified specialists who can withstand competition in the conditions of the market economy. In recent years, large-scale work has been done and is being done on the training of specialist personnel, improving its quality and efficiency. In particular, special attention is being paid to developing qualities such as independence, creativity, entrepreneurship, and activity of trained specialists.

² President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures in the Republic of Uzbekistan" On measures to prevent the activities of foreign languages to a qualitative new level "Resolution No. 5117 of May 19, 2021.

How to do independent work in educational institutions is done by each student. In order to achieve success, the student himself must work on himself with patience and without fear of difficulties. This is planned and implemented by the student himself. Problems and changes in all aspects of society affect the process of training students in higher education institutions and set new requirements. Currently, there is a great need for specialists and personnel who have theoretical knowledge and practical skills, are adaptable to changes, think freely, and can independently solve their professional and life problems. At the same time, higher education institutions require their students to be well-rounded, independent thinkers, and have organizational skills.³

The fulfillment of such requirements is ensured by teaching them to acquire knowledge throughout their life. In the conditions of active education, acquired knowledge, acquired skills and competences are formed in a systematic and logically completed manner and allow to be used in various production situations.

Activating learners allows them to develop their independent learning skills. As a solution to the problem of developing organizational skills of students in the process of independent education, we can say that the educational process in higher education institutions is gradually transferred to the credit-module system. In the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, it was indicated that by 2030, 85% of all higher education institutions in the republic should be transferred to the credit-module system.

The credit-module system is a process of educational organization and is an assessment model based on a set of module technologies of education and a credit measure. Carrying it out as a whole is a complex and systematic process. In the principle of credit module, two main issues are given importance: ensuring independent work of students; assessment of student knowledge based on rating.

Therefore, the credit-module system consists not only of teaching lessons based on innovative educational technologies, but also of teaching students to study and learn independently, to have a new attitude to education, to acquire the necessary and deep theoretical knowledge, and to form practical skills based on the demand of the labor market. In short, this system is aimed at the professional development and maturity of the student. It can be said that it is aimed at ensuring the education of a person of knowledge throughout his life and at forming human capital that can meet the labor market and modern requirements. The introduction of the credit-module system is an important factor in the cooperation between the teacher and the student.

In modular education, the pedagogue organizes, manages, advises and checks the student's learning process. And the student moves independently towards the directed object. The greatest emphasis is placed on independent education of students. Development of organizational skills of students in the process of independent education of higher education institutions is one of the main issues. In this regard, we consider it appropriate to carry out systematic work in the following directions.⁴

³ Graf, V. Fundamentals of self-organization of educational activity and independent work of students / V. Graf, I. Ilyasov, V. Lyaudis. M.: Publishing House of Moscow. floor, 1981;

⁴ Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 713-718.

- ❖ The process of teaching students in the field of reforms today is to organize the consciousness and activity of students in the framework of the students to focus on ensuring service.
- ❖ Development of experience exchanging in the promotion of teachers who have achieved success in this area.
- ❖ Today, during the digital economy, formation of independent learning information on independent education in accordance with modern requirements and registration.
- ❖ In the process of independent education, establish opportunities for the use of foreign experience in the development of organizational abilities.

Based on the above-mentioned points, it can be said that it is necessary to establish systematic work in the implementation of the independent education process in higher education institutions, to teach students to work independently, to be creative and socially active, to find their place independently in social and political life, to set promising tasks and to solve problems. will be the basis for forming a new generation of personnel with the ability to do.

High-quality communication between the teacher and the student in the process of independent work, the role and importance of the teacher in the process of independent work of students, management functions, the modern forms of independent work of students using information and communication technologies, mobile technologies - require to be covered as a pedagogical problem.

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